

by the absence of any significant drift in pH even after two hrs. This was also corroborated by taking TLC from time to time of a sample titration mixture.

In the ligand, it is the chelated phenolic (OH) group which takes part in complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ion during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one. For the proton ligand complexes, \bar{n}_A is defined as the average number of protons bound per uncomplexed ligand. From the titration curves (Fig. 1), \bar{n}_A values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated and plotted against 'B'. The plot extended over the range $0.48 < \bar{n}_A < 1.70$

Fig. 1. Titration curves 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidine-p-acetyl-aminocyaniline. Plot of 'B' vs volume of NaOH(ml).

and was wavelike. The values of pK_1^H and pK_2^H were evaluated from half integral points at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values so obtained were further corroborated by straight line plots of $\log [\bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)]$ vs B, and $\log [(2 - \bar{n}_A) / (\bar{n}_A - 1)]$ vs B respectively.

From the metal-ligand titration curves, \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The \bar{n} values were plotted against pL to get the formation curves of the metal complex equilibria. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were evaluated from these curves at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. These values were further corroborated from the straight line plots.

$\log K_2$ values for Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} could not be obtained due to the precipitation, possibly due to hydrolysis. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of $\log K_1$ values in the present investigation has been found to be $Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+} > Co^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Mg^{2+}$. The higher stability constant of Cu^{2+} complex, than what would be expected from its electronegativity, arises possibly due to Jahn-Teller distortion⁸.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDINE-p-ACETYL-AMINOANILINE WITH Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} AND Mg^{2+} AT 25° IN 75% (v/v) DIOXAN-WATER AND AT IONIC STRENGTH 0.1M $NaClO_4$

Cations	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
Log K_1	10.80	11.00	7.66	5.93	5.63	5.20
Log K_2	3.60	7.60	—	—	—	4.63

* For proton association (H^+), K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species LH and LH_2^+ while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 respectively.

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Studies of Rare Earths with Salicylhydroxamic Acid

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PREVIOUS studies with salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA), $o-C_6H_4(OH).CONHOH$ have illustrated the exceptional versatility of this chelating agent¹⁻⁸ forming the usual five-membered ring hydroxamic acid complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF Ln(SHA)₂·2H₂O COMPLEXES

Compound Ln=	Analyses				Water loss (%) ^a	Colour	Magnetic Measurement (at 28°) in B.M. ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Conductivity ^b (molar) ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	% Ln	% N	% O	% H				
La	c 22.01	6.65	39.94	3.17	5.70	White	Diamagnetic	14.30
	f 22.00	6.60	39.80	3.20	5.79			(16.20) ^c
Ce	c 22.16	6.64	39.86	3.16	5.69	Pale yellow	2.6	13.39
	f 22.20	6.74	39.75	3.22	5.68			(2.28)
Nd	c 22.66	6.59	39.58	3.14	—	Pale pink	3.8	16.16
	f 22.52	6.70	39.50	3.20	—			(11.12)
Sm	c 23.41	6.54	39.23	3.11	5.60	Yellowish	1.4	19.50
	f 23.30	6.50	39.00	3.20	5.52			(11.50)
Eu	c 23.57	6.52	39.13	3.10	—	Yellow	3.5	12.43
	f 23.55	6.60	39.00	3.15	—			(11.46)

^a temperature for water loss at 150° for La-, 135° for Ce- and 140° for Sm- complexes respectively.

^b values obtained in DMF at 28°.

^c represents concentration $M \times 10^{-4}$.

Molar conductance^o of 1 : 3 electrolyte in D. M. F. is 200-260 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹.

As an extension to our investigations on the hydroxamic acid complexes of the rare earths in order to study the influences of chelate ring sizes on the coordination number and geometry exhibited by metal complexes⁴, we have prepared and characterized some rare earth-salicylhydroxamate complexes of stoichiometry Ln(SHA)₂·2H₂O (where Ln=La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺ and Eu³⁺).

Experimental

Materials : The rare earth chlorides were prepared by dissolving appropriate rare earth oxides, 99.9% pure, in hydrochloric acid and evaporating to dryness⁵. Salicylhydroxamic acid was prepared as described by Musante⁶ and the purity of the ligand was verified by m.p. (168°) and elemental analysis.

Preparations : Rare earth chlorides (0.1M) and excess of ammonium chloride (1 gm) were dissolved together in water to which an alcoholic solution of salicylhydroxamic acid (0.3 m) was added. To this mixture ammonia solution (1 : 10) was added slowly to adjust the pH around six. The resulting complex was heated on a water bath for about half an hour with occasional stirring, filtered and washed several times with hot water and finally with 5 : 1 aqueous ethanol. The complex was then dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The reduction of any Ce(IV) to Ce(III) was done by 10% NH₂OH. HCl solution. These complexes are insoluble in chloroform, ethyl acetate, diethylether but these are found to dissolve in dimethyl formamide and mineral acids. The lanthanide content in the rare earth complexes have been determined by the method as previously described⁴. The analytical results for the new complexes are given in Table 1.

Instrumentation : The ir spectra (4000-700 cm⁻¹) were obtained from KBr pellets which were mounted on a Beckman Infrared spectrophotometer. Conductivities of the complexes were measured in dimethyl formamide solutions with the help of a

Philips Conductivity measuring bridge PR 9500. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Guoy balance. Thermal analyses were carried out with a Derivatograph (Type OD-102 Metrimplex) ; experiments were carried out in air at heating rate 4.0°/min. Compositional analyses were made using semimicro techniques. The electronic spectra of Ce(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) and Eu(III)-complexes were measured in nujol mull using spectromom 204 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data in Table 1 indicate that the complexes conform to the stoichiometry Ln(SHA)₂·2H₂O. The weight loss-temperature curve made with the compounds of La(III)-, Ce(III)- and Sm(III)-salicylhydroxamates, show the liberation of both molecules of water, which were observed to occur in the temperature range of 90° to 160° having the endothermic peaks at 120°, 110° and 115° for La-, Ce- and Sm- complexes respectively whereas the exothermic peaks were observed at (250°, 295°) for La-, (260°, 285°) for Ce- and (245°, 300°) for Sm- complexes. After this, a region of metastable state was found in each case which may be explained as due to the formation of the anhydrous compounds. An ir spectra of the anhydrous Sm(III) salicylhydroxamate has been recorded for comparison with the hydrated product. The metastable region was followed by the decomposition of the anhydrous complex over the temperature range of 180° to 300°. Further weight losses at higher temperature can be attributed to pyrolysis of initially formed anhydrous complex. Above 750°, the final residues contain all the metal as metal oxides (M₂O₃).

Magnetic susceptibility data (Table 1) are in good agreement with the theoretical values of the *f*-configuration of the metal ions calculated according to Van Vleck⁷ formula. The conductance data show that in solution all three salicylhydroxamate(SHA⁻¹) groups are bound⁸ to the metal ion.

The ir spectra of the solid complexes yielded

absorption which could be ascribed to the presence of either coordinated or lattice water. The characteristic bands of these complexes can easily be distinguished from each other from their IR spectra. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ frequency of SHA has been found to shift from 1620 to 1601 cm^{-1} in case of sodium salt whereas for the rare earth complexes a shift towards lower frequencies (1600 cm^{-1} for La^{3+} - to Eu^{3+} -complexes) has been observed. The anhydrous complex (anhydrous Sm-salicylhydroxamate) shows still further shift to 1590 cm^{-1} . The CN and NO frequencies of the free ligand shows strong bands at 1560 and 910 cm^{-1} respectively and these were displaced to 1550 and 915 cm^{-1} respectively upon complex formation. The CN band shift towards lower frequency regions whereas the NO frequency shows a shift towards higher frequency region in these complexes. A polymeric structure as obtained in the case of corresponding rare earth salicylate⁹ seems to be probable, in which each metal ion is probably attached to two coordination sites ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$ and NHO^-) in each salicylhydroxamate ions in a polymeric fashion and the coordinate $-\text{C}=\text{O} \cdots \text{Ln}-\text{O}-$ bonds¹⁰ of the lanthanosalicylhydroxamates would be expected to confer covalent character on the compound and thus reduce its electrical conductivity considerably which is corroborated by the conductivity data (Table 1). However, phenolic ($-\text{OH}$) group was remaining free. When the complexes in acetone suspension was treated with neutral FeCl_3 solution, a reddish violet colour developed¹¹. Moreover, in strongly alkaline medium, the complexes were found to be soluble, probably due to the formation of charged complex species as has been observed in the case of salicylic acid¹² and salicylhydroxamic acid¹³.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded in which the maximum absorptions have been observed at 198 and 204 nm (in hydrated Ce^{3+} salicylhydroxamate), 530, 550, 560 and 580 nm (in hydrated Nd^{3+} -salicylhydroxamate), 378, 390, 396, 402 nm (in hydrated Sm^{3+} -salicylhydroxamate) and 385, 404 nm (in hydrated Eu^{3+} -salicylhydroxamate).

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Complexes of Titanium Tetrachloride with 8-Quinolinol-N-Oxide

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STUDIES of reactions of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (HOQNO) for complexing purposes in non-aqueous media, have been very few, except for the report of formation of an adduct with SnCl_4 and disubstituted derivatives with SnCl_4 and TiCl_4 . It appeared that such reactions have not been sufficiently investigated. Present work was taken up to investigate in detail the reaction between TiCl_4 and 8-quinolinol-N-oxide.

Experimental

All operations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. 8-Quinolinol-N-oxide was prepared by the reported method².

Infrared spectra of the products formed were recorded in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} (in KBr) on Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Model-621, spectrophotometer. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for the compounds (Table 1).

Preparation of the adducts: A benzene solution of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide (in 1 and 2 mole ratios respectively) was added to a well stirred benzene solution of TiCl_4 . The red precipitate so obtained in each case was filtered, washed with chloroform and vacuum dried.

Preparation of $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OQNO})_2$: A benzene solution of 8-quinolinol-N-oxide was added to a benzene solution of TiCl_4 (1:1, 2:1 and 4:1 mole ratios respectively) and the resulting insoluble product in each case was subjected to refluxing without further isolation until the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. The red coloured insoluble product was filtered, washed and dried. In each case, the end product was found to be the same and its analysis corresponded to $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OQNO})_2$.

$\text{TiCl}_2(\text{OQNO})_2$ is also formed at room temperature when 8-quinolinol-N-oxide and TiCl_4 are mixed in the mole ratio 4:1 and kept till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased.

Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis: The TG analysis of 1:1 and 1:2 adducts were carried on Setaram G-70 Thermoanalyser in a stream of nitrogen. The results of TG analysis corresponded